

Critical Theory And Implementation Of Globalization On Teacher Education

Dr. Kalpana Subhash Pawar
Principal, Nashik

Dr. Subhash G. Pawar
K.T.H.M College, Nasik

Abstract :- The terms 'globalization' means integration of economics and societies through cross country flows of information, ideas, and goods services capital, finance, education and people. The qualitative study is an attempt to describe the concepts of a globalized teacher education. A teacher has many roles to perform. Roles of a teacher are not static but dynamic as these continue changing as per demand of society. Skills acquired and maintain through rigorous and continuing study. Various policies also limit or extend the scope of this rule. World is positive about its potential for economic and political progress in the 21st century. The teacher in the globalized environment must be prepared to think globally and act locally in matters relating to education.

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Introduction :-

The terms 'globalization' means integration of economics and societies through cross country flows of information, ideas, and goods services capital, finance and people.

Cross border integration can have several dimensions, culture, social, political and economic. In other word "The total education system of the world under one roof" it requires the unification of teaching, curriculum, and methodology and up graduation of knowledge and system.

This qualitative study is an attempt to describe the concepts of a globalized teacher education, effect of globalization in teacher education and problem of teacher education in the context of globalization. Globalization has containing both opportunities and threats for national development. It considers the recent reforms of teacher education in India and extent to which they reflect a response to global economic pressures. Any country will need to develop its own national approach to modernizing teacher education in light of the global context.

The forces and characteristics of globalization dynamics have end of traditional boundaries among nations, regions and ethnic divides. Suddenly the whole world had becomes a global village. Globalizations in historical context has a longer origin than most people are prepared to acknowledge, the two trends in the 1980's and 1990's influenced educational policies all over the world.

In education, the changes brought on by globalization have been manifested through various channels and mechanism as reforms of structures, mode of financing, administration and curriculum. In several countries, they were expressed in the adoption of neo-liberal economic policies.

The more specific trend was series of fundamental educational reforms of which changes in the structure and content of teacher education were usually a part. The rigidity and control of teacher education reform policies playing into the hegemonic ideology of globalization might also be a way to create an illusion of organization and certainly in the world that is becoming more uncertain as boundaries open up and disappear schools reforms and reforms in teacher education rely on global discourses that move from one country to another globalization does not, any way, means that national distinction become erased or that everything become identical. Today's world is changing fast both economically. And socially, while global competition is not perfect is all ways. Education has been recognized as the basic means of promoting the skill of globalization.

Our perspective is that of educator who view the current world as one that is highly internationalized and intensely global, rendering nationalistic organization obsolete. We also view education and educator as involved agents in the construction of a just social world, and content that this implies infusing the curriculum and teacher education with cosmopolitan, sensibilities, frequently, through critical theory and critical pedagogy.

Historical review has pointed to the fact that, even though globalization becomes a universal concept in the 1990's.

The implications of critical theory, technology and critical pedagogy on globalization and teacher education, particularly pertaining to teacher education in the United states.

Educational system and globalization :-

Teacher education programs should exhibit a positive approach in building up the knowledge base, in fostering innovating and interactive transactions strategies and in broadening continues and comprehensive education. All these add to build the profile of teacher full of confidence in them and in the big, wide and competitive world. In international development such as wars and world economic crises, patterns of influence with foreign states and multinational organization assistance and pressure have heavily influenced globalization of education.

Globalization should ideally be seen as a phenomenon demanding for widespread systemic changes in education. Globalization symbolizes a paradigm shift involving the re-thinking of beliefs and structures in traditional consciousness.

The goals stipulates that learning need of all young people and adults are to be meet equal access to appropriate learning and life skill programs hence the emphasize education system is committed to the promotion of science and technologies an given nation policy on education (NPE) declaration that's greater promotion of education expenditure shall continue to be devoted on education at the federal and state level and at secondary and tertiary level. The structural imbalance in the education is evident in the NPE implementation document on the transition rate of student at the end of junior secondary school and senior secondary school.

ICT has enormous implications for school curriculum planning and implementations in the era of globalization; it appears 'change' seems to become a permanent feature of human civilization. Thus the

cultivation of a permanent learning attitude and disposition become a major mission of schools all over the world.

The skills and competencies needed for survival in an era of globalization perhaps called the adoption of more innovative approaches to education.

Critical theory :-

Critical theorists strove to unmask the working of ideologies including the ways through which language and technology were used by dominant classes to maintain or create hegemony for critical theorists it was essential to unmask the working of the culture industry and the ways its distorted existing realities one of the ways through which the culture industry maintain hegemony and cohesion of civil society was through manipulating the use of language, especially through the mass media. The uncritical use of the word or concept of globalization has the potential of falling under the same category for the second generation of the Frankfurt school, education and the media were central instruments of mass deception that facilitated the manipulation of social needs and wants.

Teacher Education and Globalization:-

Habermas observed that there were at least three major tasks of a university in a democracy. Among these were “the transmission of technically exploitable knowledge” raising the “political consciousness of its students” and ensuring that graduates are equipped, no matter how indirectly with a minimum of qualification in the era of extra functional abilities, “one could ask, how are these task met in teacher education programs in the united states?” McLaren (2003) views education as implicate in the labor force and labor production. Within the context of preparing teachers for working in a global world habermas’s challenge called for educators to be knowledgeable and politically aware. The political enlighten of the student that Habermas sees as important is central to understanding and contesting the ideologies of globalization .A major characteristic of the enlighten was its slow response to critiquing domination and exploitation. In general, what the west called progress was the subjugation of the others, if universities in the west have been training students for domination then preparing teachers for a global world called for transforming the general orientation of the universities as well as the teachers education program. The project of modernity is positively appropriated university and teacher education program need to be more democratic. The implications are that educations have not kept pace with social and technologies changes in such circumstances, globalization defects globalism.

Critical theorists lament the absence of global awareness and political agency in teacher education and education programs.

In any educational systems, the teacher performs a significant function of perpetuating society’s heritage and emerging human resources towards social progress. The level of a nation’s education cannot rise far above the quality of teacher of that nation. This there for, makes the preparation and selection of teachers a significance social concern. There is a need to review and transform both the professional in preparation of teacher and their in-service training. There is little doubt that likes all developing countries, educational particularly in its quest to achieve education for all by 2020. Undoubtedly, teachers

lie at the heart of this educational crisis because only the teacher who passes the necessary technical competence and professional skills through a well coordinated teachers. Educational program can rise to meet the challenges of the crisis.

A learning environment that seeks student's cooperation and minimizes disciplinary problems would be achieved by teacher who has expertise in content and instructional strategies, who make wise decisions about time and space, who demonstrate an attitude of valuing and caring their students. Classroom management is not an end in itself but indicate of teacher's authority, inner strength interpersonal relations and leadership role preventive classroom management can be effected by planning rules and procedures before hand as well as developing. Students accountability is depend on their academic work and classroom behavior. The development of personality traits and cultivation of skills required for effective management is be achieve through theory practice and effective monitoring.

The education commission recommended introduction of a sound program of professional education of teachers. It further remark that investment in teacher education can yield very rich dividends because the functional resources required are small when measured against the resulting improvements in the education of millions. The focus of teachers training should depart from the traditional method of professional teacher educational program. Which thus far has not produces the desired quality and professionalism. The system exposes the teachers to acquire the body of knowledge in a subject discipline. In the cores of education which involves methodology of teaching learning. Through a supervised teaching practice which is referred to as apprentice. This system has not produced the desired result for a transformative educational system in a globalized world innovation require for both for teachers pre-service preparation and teachers in-service training. It is for this reason the school based teacher professional preparation and development is advocated. This enables schools and teachers to play a much larger role in teacher's professional development. This will eventually makes the schools be the first to reap benefits of generations of good new teachers. The cluster school-based teacher in service teacher development is an innovation being carried out. The goal of global competitiveness demands that both the curriculum and the teaching methods to be more focused on developing generic and altitudinal skills such as critical thinking and problem solving as well as promoting national reconciliation. The efforts to reform and repositions educated to meet the challenges of globalization era have not be yielding the requisite results largely because enough attention has not been given to the roles and instrumentality of educational assessment in initiating and sustaining educational reforms.

The primary goals of authentic assessment which appears with the educational needs of contemporary globalized era are:-

1. To develop the learners cognitive strategies for self monitoring of progress.
2. To faster the learners ability for higher order thinking skills.
3. To measure the progress against learners own development, not be norm.
4. To provide more accurate evidence of a learners abilities than traditional tests.

The emphasis of education in globalised societies is to create a cultural that is learning friendly. Most societies must set up cooperative learning environment where in all resources in the community are more learning friendly. Corresponding innovations in educational assessment should also be learners friendly and performance focused, the movements variously called authentic assessment which are in wide variety of forms such as computer simulations open ended questions, demonstrations, exhibits, writing in many disciplines and portfolios of students works overtime. All these are due to globalized necessity for more meaningful assessment policies that will move accurately captured the vital learning out comes that students must achieves in order to survive and achieve success in contemporary societies.

It should perhaps be impossible for any citizen of globalised world to acquire basic education without adequate proficiency in the use of ICT.

Conclusion:-

A teacher has many roles to perform. Identification and standardization of these roles is helpful in involving a teaching portfolio. Roles of a teacher are not static but dynamic as these continue changing as per demand of society. Teaching is a profession, which requires expert knowledge and specialized. Skills acquired and maintain through rigorous and continuing study. Various policies also limit or extend the scope of this rule. World is positive about its potential for economic and political progress in the 21st century. The trends and characteristics of globalization perhaps called for a total re-invention of teaching profession. The teacher in the globalized environment must be prepared to think globally and act locally in matters relating to education.

Ministry of education in countries need to radically change their teachers promotion policy if they sincerely interested in keeping a teaching manpower with high morale for globalized society that is perennially on the move for positive changes. Educational system will not be modernized until the whole system of teacher training is drastically over hauled, intellectually richer, and more challenging.

References:-

- 1) Kishan N R, Global Trends in Teacher Education 2007
- 2) Tendons S. (2005), Globalization : Impact on Education
- 3) Robertson R.(1992) Globalization : Social theory and global culture, London.
- 4) McLaren P. and R.Faranmandpur, (2005), teaching against global capitalism and the new imperialism.
- 5) Capella, J. (2000) Globalization and education : critical perspectives, London
- 6) Barbules, N (2000) "Does the internet constitute a Global Educational Community".
- 7) Mark malisa, Randall koetting (2007), "Globalization and Teacher education in a technocratic era".
- 8) www.ugc.ac.in
- 9) <http://www.ncert.nic.in>
- 10) www.education.nic.in
- 11) <http://ssrn.com/bstract>
- 12) Srikant misra, Arti bajpai, "implication of Globalization on Education".